

MEDICAL SCIENCES

GLYCATED HEMOGLOBIN (HbA1c) AS A MEANS OF ASSESSING LONG-TERM CONTROL IN TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS

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Abstract

Objective: To evaluate the reliability of HbA1c as an indicator of glycemic control in type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM) depending on the therapeutic regimen.

Materials and methods: We followed 85 patients (50 men, 35 women, average age 58.79 ± 12.82 years) with DM type 2 (31 patients not taking insulin therapy - group 1, 33 patients taking pre-mixed insulin - group 2, 21 patients on multiple insulin injections, group 3). Patients had repeated fasting and postprandial blood glucose measurements over three months. HbA1c was measured at the beginning and at the end of this period. The correlation between HbA1c and blood glucose measurements at different times of the day was reported.

Results: In group 1, the correlation coefficient with the average glucose is $r = 0.699$, $p < 0.01$, in group 2 - $r = 0.452$, $p < 0.01$, in the group of intensive insulin treatment, no correlation was found $r = 0.308$. In insulin-naïve patients and those treated with premixed insulins, HbA1c showed a good correlation with mean blood glucose before and after breakfast, before and after lunch, before and after dinner, before and after lunch, before and after dinner, before bedtime and at night ($p < 0.05$). There was no such correlation in the intensive care group. No correlation was found with the change in glucose in any of the groups.

Conclusion: In patients with type 2 diabetes receiving oral treatment or premixed insulin, HbA1c is a valuable method to assess control. With an intensified insulin regimen, a good correlation of HbA1c is not reported, it should only be used in combination with blood sugar monitoring.

Keywords: glycated hemoglobin, glucose control, therapeutic regimen.

Introduction: Glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) is the generally accepted gold standard for assessing glycemic control in diabetes mellitus. HbA1c values are the result of chronic exposure to glucose for 2-3 months and are determined from both fasting and postprandial glycemia in each individual. Glycated hemoglobin is an index of the average glucose levels during the last few months and is directly related to the survival of erythrocytes (on average about 120 days) at any time the value of glycated hemoglobin is determined by all red blood cells present in the circulation - both the oldest and from the youngest. Recent plasma glycemia (in the last 3-4 weeks) contribute to the HbA1c level to a greater extent than those back in time. Blood sugars in the last 30 days determine about 50% of the final result, and blood sugars from 90-120 days earlier determine 10% (1,2). This explains why, although they reflect a relatively long period of 2-3 months, glycated hemoglobin levels can change relatively quickly with significant changes in blood sugars and ultimately the reported changes as a statute of limitations be smaller than these for 120 days. The HbA1c test is much more conservative in terms of the conditions under which it is conducted compared to the measurement of venous glucose. It can be performed at any time of the day, does not require special preparation before the test such as a certain diet or fasting, and has long-term stability when collecting and storing blood under the specified conditions. As we noted, with a normal lifespan of

erythrocytes, HbA1c is a reliable indicator of the glycemic status in the last 8-12 weeks. The accuracy of glycine hemoglobin testing is affected by factors that affect erythrocyte viability, as well as non-enzymatic glycation of hemoglobin. Hematologic conditions such as hemoglobin variants, iron deficiency, hemolytic anemia, presence of carbamylated hemoglobin in uremia, various other specific conditions including dyslipidemia, malignancies, liver cirrhosis, certain medications, and also pregnancy are among the factors that affect HbA1c measurements (3)

The interactions between blood sugars and HbA1c are extremely complicated and complex. A number of studies have tracked the correlations between blood sugars in different parts of the day and glycated hemoglobin (4-6). Blood sugars before lunch and those in the earlier stages of the follow-up period showed less correlation with HbA1c than those after lunch and in the later stages (7). A number of studies confirm that the contribution of postprandial glycemia is greater at lower HbA1c values. With a glycated hemoglobin of 6.5%, almost 90% of its value is determined by postprandial glycemia. At the same time, 9.0% 40% are the result of postprandial glycemia (8). Although intra-individual variations in HbA1c are minimal, there is evidence of wide fluctuations in HbA1c values between different individuals that are unrelated to glycemic status and that define patients as (poor or

slow glycaters) and (strong or rapid glycaters) depending from the rate of glycation of proteins (9). Fast glycaters have a consistently higher HbA1c level than expected for their respective mean glycemia, while the reverse is true for slow glycaters. Proposed explanations suggest inter-individual differences in tissue glycation, in factors affecting membrane permeability to glucose or binding to hemoglobin, and also genetic factors (10). Some authors believe that glycated hemoglobin and its levels show racial differences, regardless of glycemic levels. For example, according to a meta-analyst, representatives of the black race have higher levels compared to the white race (differences up to 0.65% are reported) 11. However, there is no unity of opinion on this issue. Many studies have compared time-of-day blood glucose levels with HbA1c levels, showing that postprandial blood glucose levels are more strongly associated with HbA1c levels (12-14). The proven simple linear regression relationship is characteristic both for the stable course of the DM disease and for the initiation of initial intensive treatment (15). Numerous data are accumulating that glycated hemoglobin, assessed alone, is insufficient for an adequate assessment of the metabolic situation in patients with DM. Risk of developing DM-related complications obviously depends not only on long-term glucose values, but also on the presence and occurrence of short-term glycemic peaks and troughs lasting from minutes to hours at the beginning of the day. Glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) is mainly used to assess long-term glycemic control in patients with type 1 and type 2 DM. The question arises to what extent the therapeutic regimen is related to the levels of glycated hemoglobin and whether there is a correlation between these levels and the respective applied therapy, regardless of the glycemic values.

Materials and methods:

In order to establish the relationship between glycated hemoglobin and the applied therapy in DM type 2, we conducted a follow-up among 85 patients. Depending on the type of treatment, the study group was divided into three subgroups.

- Group 1, not carrying out insulin treatment – 31 patients;
- Group 2, conducting treatments with premixed insulin – 33 patients;
- Group 3, conducting treatments with multiple insulin injections – 21 patients.

A precise medical history was taken of the patients, taking into account age, duration of the disease, ongoing treatment, accompanying diseases and emerging complications. The study did not include patients with severe accompanying diseases, liver and kidney failure, patients with existing iron deficiency or other anemia, pregnancy or other conditions that would affect the control of the disease and the parameters for its follow-up. Patients were followed for a 12-week period and asked to perform an 8-time profile (blood sugar before breakfast, lunch and dinner, blood sugar 2 hours after breakfast, lunch and dinner, before bed and at 03:00 am) for at least 3 days in the week. The patients themselves determined on which day of the week they would perform the measurements, being encouraged to carry out additional measurements on other days. The

study used the same type of glucometers (Optium Exceed) in order to avoid technical inconsistencies. In order to facilitate the patients at the beginning of the follow-up, a diary with instructions for recording the measured values was provided.

HbA1c was measured at the beginning and end of this period. The correlation between HbA1c and blood glucose measurements at different time points was reported, comparing the results in the different treatment groups. The critical level of significance used is $\alpha=0.05$. The corresponding null hypothesis is rejected when P values (p -value) is smaller than α . SPSS version 16.0 for Windows was used for the mathematical processing of the data

Results

Of the 85 patients included in the study, 50 were men and 35 were women. the average age of the studied group was 58.79 ± 12.82 years. The patients were diagnosed with DM type 2 with a history of 10.61 ± 6.03 years. Table 1 presents the characteristics of the included patients by group. The distribution by gender shows differences and not homogeneity in the individual groups, because patient selection was random and based on patients' willingness to participate in follow-up. The patients were of similar mean age, with no significant statistical difference. Differences were also noted in the duration of the disease between the individual groups. There was a shorter duration of the disease in patients with diabetes type 2 on oral treatment (8.06 ± 5.86 years, $P<0.05$) compared to the other groups. Regarding glycemic control at baseline, assessed by HbA1c, there were no significant differences between the different groups. The patients' therapy was not changed during the observed period. Patients on insulin treatment changed only the dosage regimen according to the diet and exercise regime. It is important to note that each of the patients underwent a training course on dietary and physical activity in DM treatment.

Table 2 provides data on the correlations between HbA1c and blood glucose levels at different times of the day in the different treatment groups. In group 1, the correlation coefficient with average glucose is $r=0.699$, $p<0.01$, in group 2 $r=0.452$, $p<0.01$. In the multiple injection group (group 3), no significant correlation $r=0.308$ was found. In patients not treated with insulin and in patients treated with premixed insulin, CBA showed a good correlation with mean blood glucose before and after breakfast, before and after lunch, before and after dinner, before bed and at 03:00 at night ($p<0.05$). There is no such correlation in the group of intensified insulin treatment. Group 1 (not receiving insulin therapy) a highly significant correlation was observed for each subperiod and in general for the mean glycemic values before breakfast, before lunch, after lunch, before dinner, after dinner and at night. For the entire observed period in group 2 (patients treated with premixed insulin) a good correlation dependence was established between average glycemia and HbA1c. During the individual periods, the correlation is consistently good for glycemia before breakfast, after breakfast, before lunch, after lunch, before dinner and after

dinner. The highest correlation is with blood sugars after lunch ($r=0.709$) and before dinner ($r=0.531$) and with low significance is that before going to bed ($r=0.528$) and at night ($r=0.409$). In general, compared to group 1, relatively weaker correlation dependences are observed, in the cases of such an established one, except for those in the hours after eating after lunch, where the correlation is stronger for group 2. Group 3 observed a low degree of correlation between average blood sugars for the entire period and HbA1c ($r=0.308$). A similar correlation was also observed for blood sugars after lunch ($r=0.360$) and before breakfast ($r=0.354$). The variability between individual periods, however, is more pronounced in preprandial hours, after dinner and before bed. Therefore, in patients with type 2 diabetes on intensified insulin treatment, the relationship between HbA1c and average glycemia is not so clearly expressed, blood glucose measurements cannot well predict HbA1c levels and vice versa. Taking into account the standard deviation of blood sugars, the dependence of HbA1c and variations of blood sugars was investigated. Each treatment group was considered independently, but no correlation with standard deviation was found. HbA1c was not able to reflect the variability of glycemia in any treatment group.

Discussion

The importance of HbA1c for assessing glycemic control is generally accepted in clinical practice. Glycated hemoglobin is an indicator that defines the long-term control of the DM disease, the need for a change in therapy, and recently it is also used to diagnose states of carbohydrate metabolism disorders (16). HbA1c has been officially accepted as criteria for the diagnosis of DM despite still existing controversies in this aspect (17). To what extent the levels of the registered glycated hemoglobin depend on the type of treatment applied (not on the specifically applied medication) and how much in the different groups HbA1c is dependent on the different types of therapy is a question poorly represented in the scientific literature.

Multiple studies to date involving follow-up with modern continuous glucose monitoring (CGM) systems have reported similar HbA1c values in patients with significant differences in course and glycemic control. The same glycated hemoglobin in these cases is registered with highly varying or non-varying blood sugars. On the one hand, HbA1c correlates most strongly with the average value of blood sugars, and rapid fluctuations of the latter do not affect its levels. Practical tools such as continuous glucose monitoring (CGM) systems provide good information about patients' overall glucose control. In certain groups of patients (for example, those on hemodialysis), glycated hemoglobin is an unreliable indicator and continuous glucose monitoring is the tool of choice. The use of (CGM) continues to be limited, especially in patients with DM type 2, for various reasons (cost, lack of motivation, inconvenience). At the same time, these systems reflect a relatively short observation period with a single application (up to 7 days).

HbA1c remains the main tool used to assess control in type 2 DM. Most likely, the variability of blood

sugars is the factor determining the reliability of glycated hemoglobin in its use in non-insulin-treated patients and in those using premixed insulin (probably in these groups the disease proceeds relatively stably). In patients with DM type 2 treated with intensified insulin therapy, the variability of glycemia is greater, which is determined by the type of treatment itself and the nature of the disease.

In our study, patients had no statistically significant difference in age and initial assessed disease control (initial HbA1c). Thus, these factors were excluded as influencing glycemic levels during follow-up and final HbA1c. Discussing the results, we determined the indirect conclusion that HbA1c levels in patients with intensified insulin therapy are not a completely reliable indicator of glycemic control, in contrast to groups conducting insulin treatment or treated with premixed insulin, where this indicator correlates well with measured sugars and determines a significant degree of reliance on it as an indicator of control evaluation.

The relatively small number of studied patients in the different groups is a major drawback of the study. Despite the statistically significant differences and data, confirmation of the results in larger cohorts would help to clarify these inconsistencies and would allow for a more complete assessment of the described dependencies.

Conclusion:

Based on the obtained data, we concluded that in type 2 DM patients receiving oral treatment or premixed insulin, HbA1c is a valuable method for assessing long-term control. In cases treated with multiple daily insulin injections, HbA1c does not correlate strictly with blood glucose measurements and should be used as a control assessment only in combination with self-monitoring of blood glucose. It is necessary to search for new, more reliable methods for evaluating glycemic control in some therapeutic groups.

References

1. Zendjibal M. The glycated hemoglobin: indication, interpretation and limitations. *Ann Pharm Fr* 2015;73(5): 336-339.
2. Markis K, Spanou L. Is There a Relationship between mean blood glucose and glycated hemoglobin? / *Diab Sci Tech* 2011; 5(6): 564-567.
3. Bloomgarten ZT. A1c: recommendations, debates and questions. *Diab Care* 2009; 32 (12): e141-147.
4. Ketema E, Kibret K. Correlation of fasting and postprandial plasma glucose with HbA1c in assessing glycemic control; systematic review and meta-analysis. *Arch publ Health* 2015; 73: 43-46
5. Gupta S, Puppalwar P, Chala A. Correlation of fasting and post meal plasma glucose level to increased HbA1c levels in type-2 diabetes mellitus. *Int) Adv Med* 2014, 1 (2): 127-131.
6. Chubb SA, Van Minnenk M, David WA, Bruce DG, Davis TA. The relationship between self-monitoring of blood glucose result and glycated haemoglobin in type 2 diabetes: the fremantle diabetes study. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract* 2011; 94 (3) 371-376.

7. Kazmi NH, Gillani S, Afzal S, Hussain S. Correlation between glycated haemoglobin levels and random blood glucose. / *Ayub Med Coll Abbottabad* 2013; 25(1-2): 86-88.
8. Monnier L, Lapinski H, Colette C. Contributions of fasting and postprandial glucose increments to the overall diurnal hyperglucemia of type 2 diabetic patients: variations with increasing levels of HbA1c. *Diab Care* 2003; 26: 881-885.
9. Gallagher Ej, Le Rolth D, Bloomgarden Z. Review of Haemoglobin A1c in the management of diabetes. / *Diabetes* 2009; 1: 9-17.
10. Hempe JM, Gomez R, Mc Carter RJ Jr, Chalew SA. High and low hemoglobin glycation phenotypes in type 1 diabetes: challenge for interpretation of glycemic control. / *Diab Compl* 2002; 16 (15): 313-320.
11. Sacks D. Hemoglobin A1c and Race: Should Therapeutic Targets and Diagnostic Cutoffs Differ among Racial Groups? *Clin Chem* 2016; 62 (9): 1199-1201.
12. Levetan CS, Jeng LM, Thornton KR, Want L, Ratner RE. When do glucose values best correlate with hemoglobin A1c? *Diabetes* 2001; 50 (2suppl):A 124.
13. Bonora E, Calcaterra F, Lombardi S, Bonfante N, Formentini G, Bonadonna RC, et al. Plasma glucose levels throughout the day and HbA1c interrelationship in type 2 diabetes: implication for treatment and monitoring of metabolic control. *Diab Care* 2001; 24 (12): 2023-2029.
14. Kovatchev BP, Cox DJ, Strauma M, Fahry LS. Association of self monitoring blood glucose profiles with glycosylated hemoglobin in patients with insulin dependent diabetes *Methods Enzymol* 2000; 321: 410-417.
15. Barua A, Acharya J, Ghaskadbi S, Goel P. The relationship between fasting plasma glucose and HbA1c during intensive periods of glucose control in antidiabetic therapy. / *Theor Biol* 2014; 363:158-163.
16. Welsh K, Kirkman M, Sacks D. Role of glycosylated proteins in the diagnosis and management of diabetes: research gaps and future directions *Diab Care* 2016; 39(3): 1299-1306.
17. Ribeiro R, Macedo M, Raposo J, Tavares R, Paula M, Filipe J. HbA1c fructosamine and glycosylated albumin in the detection of glycaemic conditions. *Curr Diab Review* 2016; 12 (1), 14-19.
18. Meyer L, Chantrel F, Imhoff O, Sissoko A, Serb L, Dorey F et al. Glycated albumin and continuous glucose monitoring to replace glycosylated haemoglobin in patients with diabetes treated with haemodialysis. *Diabetic Medicine* 2013; 10 (30): 1388-1389.

CARDIOVASCULAR RISK ASSESSMENT IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE 1 DIABETES MELLITUS

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Abstract

Cardiovascular disease (CVD) is a major cause of death in type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM). Management of CVD risk factors in T1DM patients is based on evidence, mostly extrapolated from T2DM studies. Hyperglycemia, leading to the induction of oxidative stress, is considered a key pathophysiological mechanism for the development of micro- and macrovascular complications. Biochemical processes related to it directly damage monocyte function, and also indirectly affect the function of monocyte cells, through the synthesis of growth factors, cytokines and vasoactive mediators in other cells. However, the epidemiologic relationship between glycemia and CVD is not fully understood. The aim of the present review is a systematic analysis of potential laboratory biomarkers for the assessment of cardiovascular risk in T1DM patients, with particular attention paid to asymmetric dimethylarginine (ADMA), adiponectin (ADPN) and osteoprotegerin (OPG) as such. The available literature suggests a significant burden of CVD in patients with T1DM and poor management of risk factors. This is based on the poor evidence base for therapeutic management of CVD risk in T1DM patients. The clinical implications of the epidemiological and pathophysiological aspects of the relationship between T1DM and CVD are discussed. We have reviewed the available literature noting areas where sufficient clarity is lacking. More and more clinical studies are validating the capabilities of new classes of laboratory biomarkers that characterize cardiovascular changes in patients with T1DM.

Keywords: type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM), cardiovascular disease (CVD), hyperglycemia, oxidative stress, endothelial dysfunction, laboratory biomarkers.

Introduction

Cardiovascular disease (CVD) is a major cause of death in patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM). The evidence for this is mainly extrapolated from studies of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus

(T2DM). Based on a systematic analysis of literature data, it is established that a significant number of patients with T1DM are exposed to cardiovascular risk factors. When following the progression of T1DM, it is reported that the first cases of clinically manifested